

THE IMPORTANCE OF STRENGTHENING LESSONS IN STUDENTS 'MOTHER TONGUE AND READING LITERACY

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Annotation: This article discusses the importance of a new modern Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy textbook in enhancing students' knowledge and the importance of strengthening lessons in teaching Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy to students.

Keywords: Mother tongue and reading literacy, elementary school, pedagogical technology, dominoes, role-playing games, brainstorming, reinforcement lessons
The sections studied are taken into account in the organization of lessons to strengthen mother tongue and reading literacy. After each new topic, the topic is repeated during the lesson and before the next new topic statement. It is achieved by strengthening the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students.

"In the primary school, mother tongue and reading literacy classes are important among other subjects because of their content, students' thinking, thinking, worldview, talent, speech, and personality development." [1] Students' reading and writing skills improve during mother tongue and reading literacy classes. Students will develop the ability to write beautifully, without errors, in calligraphy, and to read fluently, consciously, expressively, to understand the idea of a work of art, and to express their views on a work or event." [2]

Reading and working on a variety of poems, stories, and proverbs in the Mother Tongue and Reading Literacy book expands students' understanding of existence and reality.

Vocabulary work is also important in creating new concepts in students, in identifying new features of objects, in generalizing ideas in the use of vocabulary-rich words in a new space. "Explaining the meaning of words and phrases, such as conscience, society, etc., especially in the abstract national context, helps to develop students' thinking and aesthetic pleasures." [3]

"From the earliest days of education, students learn about nature, society, human labor and animal life, and a number of other things." [4]

"Strengthening and training courses are part of the design process. The soundness of the knowledge taught in the mother tongue and reading literacy depends to a large extent on the teacher's organization of reinforcement classes." [5] In such lessons, the student returns to the theoretical knowledge and grammar rules previously taught. During the exercise, the student acts according

to the rules he has learned. In reinforcement lessons, previously perceived knowledge is re-imagined.

Reinforcement classes, on the one hand, focus on developing students 'skills through a variety of exercises, and on the other hand, serve to clarify and expand students' knowledge.

“Reinforcement lessons are very different from new material lessons. While new topics are based on language phenomena that students do not understand and are abstract to them, reinforcement lessons are based on rules that students have been taught but have not fully mastered, and that they follow what they have learned. [6]

Reinforcement classes use a variety of exercises. Students' activities are organized around the linguistic evidence for the rules taught. Another important feature of this type of course is the development of skills in students.

"The most important feature of a reinforcement lesson is that it is a continuation of the new material and reinforcement lessons, and is organized in connection with it." [7]

The importance of reinforcement lessons in primary school is that they are based on the study of mother tongue and reading literacy materials not on a theoretical basis but on a practical basis. The method of strengthening the sections of the native language and reading literacy: phonetics, morphology, syntax is used effectively.

This is because it is widely used to reinforce this knowledge in the minds of students. This is because students will not be able to master this knowledge without consolidation.

“Strengthening cannot be done on its own without mother tongue and reading literacy being separated from other teaching methods. Its implementation requires a combination of other methods. Because the method of comparison is also used effectively when repeating topics. The first of these necessarily requires the second.” [8]

The main purpose of mother tongue and reading literacy classes is to apply the topics covered in written and oral presentations, and secondly, to ensure that the knowledge is memorized in a timely manner.

"The reinforcement method ensures that students acquire knowledge thoroughly, answer questions in a timely manner, and that students complete their independent work on time." [9]

Elementary school students are stubborn and get tired quickly during class. Lessons taught in the same way cause them to feel bored. Therefore, in the

second and fourth stages of the lesson, a skilled teacher uses a variety of didactic games and interactive methods in the process of strengthening. This leads to an increase in students' interest in learning. Of course, the methods and techniques used by the teacher are chosen based on the content of each topic being studied. A well-organized lesson will help the student to master the topic well and completely.

"It is useful for teachers to use a variety of methods and didactic games to effectively organize reinforcement lessons in the primary school. Let's look at some examples from them. " [10]

Working in small groups. Students are divided into small groups of five or six to discuss the problem freely. For example, in this group, they analyze and state the opinions of each member or student they have identified.

These groups can be organized randomly. For example, "white, red, black, green, yellow" are given. The "whites" are the first subgroup, the "reds" are the second subgroup and the second method: first the best 6 students are identified, then the relatively low-achieving students are divided into 5-6 groups, and then the low-achieving students are divided into equal groups. These groups operate on a regular basis.

"Museum" and presentation - a free discussion of the topic of the lesson. Based on the above considerations, we can call reinforcement lessons skills development lessons.

Brainstorming is as short, concise, and concise as possible, time-limited, and quick. Opinions expressed in the form of cues are also accepted and taken into account.

Role-playing games are dramas, simulations, and screenplays. Each participant must be able to clearly understand the character's point of view and speak on his or her behalf. Through this game, students should learn certain lessons and conclusions.

"Creative activity" - drawing, writing creative essays, role-playing, etc.

"Problem situations" are situations that are created and discussed in small groups and individually.

Domino Game - Prerequisite: The game continues by finding a word that begins with the letter that ends with each letter, thus creating a unique chain of words. For example, a planned worker, an exemplary, hardworking, smart, industrious, restless, non-linear, intelligent, ignorant, poisonous ... This encourages students to recall what they have learned about word structure and to develop the ability to apply it in practice.

Find Your Word Game - In this game, students are divided into 3 groups. The children in each group will have to choose the words for the task given by the teacher from the given text. For example, the first group of students selects words from the noun phrase, the second group of students selects words from the adjective group, and the third group of students selects words from the verb group. You will need a teacher-made portable board or cardboard. All three groups begin to complete the task. The group that finds the words that belong to them quickly and correctly is the winner, and is encouraged by the teacher and students.

Words: Potato, sweet, desk, soil, black, likes, pleasing, came, apple, red, salty, cotton, air, water, close, sound, vibrated, beautiful, tree, green, thirsty, came out, broke.

"Saw method - According to this method, a small group of 5 students. All group members work on a single assignment based on the learning material. Within the group, students divide the assignments into parts. Each student becomes a "specialist" by mastering his or her own subject. At the end of the lesson, a meeting of "experts" in each subgroup will be held in reorganized groups. [11]

Say the Right Game - This game reinforces students' knowledge of words with opposite meanings. Say the opposite also encourages children to be smart and to teach them to be responsible now. Motion games can also be used to increase the interest and activity of each student. To do this, the teacher throws a ball to the student to say a word and say a word that means the opposite, and when the student says the answer, he returns the ball to the teacher. The game continues in this way. The class is ready to answer the questions.

Thus, reinforcement lessons are a guarantee and a means for students to fully master the basics of science.

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